

Review Article

Modern Trends in Albanian Theatre After 1990

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Abstract

This study examines the development of modern and postmodern trends in Albanian theatre after the 1990s, a period marked by profound political and cultural transformation following the collapse of the communist regime. The restoration of artistic freedom created new opportunities for experimentation in dramaturgy and stage direction, allowing Albanian theatre practitioners to engage more openly with contemporary European and global theatrical models. The article analyses the evolution of theatrical aesthetics, directing concepts, and dramaturgical structures that emerged in Albania and Kosovo during this period. Special attention is given to the influence of modernist and postmodernist dramaturgy, including avant-garde experimentation, fragmentation of narrative structure, symbolic staging, and the increased role of the actor's expressive performance. The study also explores the reception and adaptation of the Theatre of the Absurd in Albanian theatre, particularly through the staging of works by prominent playwrights such as Samuel Beckett and Eugene Ionesco. Through the analysis of several theatrical productions and dramaturgical works by Albanian authors and directors, the article highlights the ways in which Albanian theatre has incorporated elements such as symbolic space, fragmented dialogue, grotesque aesthetics, and existential themes. These elements have contributed to the transformation of theatrical language and the reinterpretation of human relationships, identity, and social reality in the post-communist context. The research demonstrates that Albanian theatre after 1990 has gradually integrated modern and postmodern dramaturgical models while maintaining its own cultural and historical specificity. As a result, contemporary Albanian theatre reflects a dynamic synthesis of local artistic traditions and global theatrical influences.

Keywords: Albanian Theatre; Modern Drama; Postmodern Theatre; Dramaturgy, Stage Directing; Post-Communist Culture.

1. Introduction

Modernist and postmodernist trends in Albanian drama and theatre, in fact, appeared in full only after 1990, when freedom of artistic expression was legitimized with the overthrow of communism and the establishment of democracy. The works staged during this period 1990-2025, both those that came from world dramaturgy models, as well as those that came from Albanian dramaturgy models (Albania, Kosovo, Macedonia, etc.), which applied the principles of modern European and world dramaturgy and theatre,

strongly influenced the new artistic form and situation of Albanian theatre. They gave them another look and style, offering, consequently, the innovation of the artistic language with previously unprecedented theatrical models. Directors before 1990 such as Pirro Mani, Serafin Fanku, Mihal Luarasi, Kujtim Spahivogli, Gëzim Kame, especially the new generation of directors of the '90s and onwards such as Altin Basha, Arben Kumbaro, Hervin Çuli, Memet Xhelili, Milto Kutali, Kiço Londo etc., reflected the mobility of directorial thought, the dissatisfaction with the traditional forms and typologies of former conceptions, by implementing applications of a much more advanced artistic language than before in the theatre.

The directors quickly embraced the models that the world theatre had offered through the treatments of modernist and avant-garde drama since the beginning of the 20th century and until later. The formal elements and the new theatrical aesthetics offered the Albanian spectator another way of artistic expression. They emancipated both his tastes and the tastes of the acting staff and other participating arts. The theatre artists adopted the latest world theatre experiences and created the conditions for the implementation of poetics and models that were dictated by the modern texts of avant-garde and modernist dramas themselves with new forms and ways of presenting “differently” human relationships as well as the world around them. Thanks to this innovative dioptré and with profound philosophical stratifications, in the most fortunate cases the Albanian theatre managed to discover the psychological underpinnings of the characters, the traumas of the man of the time in a consumer society and with often misunderstood freedom, embodied as essential, important phenomena, which are often covered by a mythical, mystical or esoteric garment.

In numerous performances the Albanian theatre offered interactive and reciprocal relationships with the often-symbolic conceptions of the decorations and stage space, of the costumes, of the treatment of the actors' makeup, of the actors' manner of acting, of the choreography and movement in general, of the *mise-en-scène*, etc. Taken together and in their ideological and stylistic cohesion, they led the expected thematic and motivational trends of Albanian theatre after 1990.

2. Literature Review

As is known, prominent playwrights and directors of the first half of the 20th century in Europe embraced the avant-garde with its bold experimentation and radical rejection of classical realistic forms and their frozen structures. They widely introduced some abandoned theatrical components, which became an integral part of the performance, such as music, painting, choreography, the element of the Chorus, the fragmentation of the subject, ritual, cinematic image, the language of symbols, etc. These features were also embraced by Albanian playwrights in Albania and Kosovo. According to the modern and postmodern model, many performances were performed in Albanian theatre in which the spectators sat around the actors, in open environments, on the stage square or in other places such as schoolyards, public squares, tourist resorts, museums, bar-restaurants,

which were not truly like classical theatre stages. In Albanian authors, the new model of drama appeared as the formation of the New, of the Breaking, as a project of the Unfinished. There, the well-known notion of Absence gained priority, which over time passed to Self-Presence and Emptiness in Fullness. This phenomenon was observed in the dramaturgical approaches of postmodernism in the works of Anton Pashku, Teki Dervishi, Rexhep Qosja, Beqir Musliu, Mehmet Krajë, Kasem Trebeshinë, Minush Jeros, Stefan Çapalik, Ferdinand Hysi, Haqif Mulliq, Jeton Neziraj, etc. In many of the stage plays of these authors, the principles of postmodernism were successfully applied. In many performances, the clichés and schemes of traditional classical drama and theater were already challenged. They were raised against sublime, tragic contents, with “great” meanings and significance, with universal structures and “absolute” truths, insisting more on the spiritual crises and fractures of man. Often this man was ordinary, commonplace, small, like a fragmented individual. Now the authors and directors of the performances use parody of characters, irony and the grotesque, mockery of everything.

There are no more “holy” or “great” characters. Everyone is dirty, traumatic, and ridiculous. From a formal point of view, our theatre used the fragmentation of the subject, where each fragment maintained its integrity. Tragicomedy becomes the favorite form of playwrights and directors. It possesses elements of pop, street, linguistic jargon, and swearing. The plays are often treated as a “game,” as entertainment, even inviting the audience to participate in the process of the game, of the theatrical event (happening). In their plays and performances, the authors and directors have highlighted the conflict between moral, philosophical, or religious principles with a depraved society, existential contradictions, and the right starting points of a social action or mission with their wrong ending. Personal catastrophes are projected as societal catastrophes and vice versa.

This dramaturgical technique has been followed by dramatists Ferdinand Hysi in several plays such as “In front of traffic light”, “Carriage Horse”, “Dog of Dog” and “Three Minds at Auction”, Stefan Çapaliku in some drama such as “Invitation to Dinner”, “Three Love Song”, “Utopos”, “Alegretto Albania”, “Faust from Tirana”, “Shoes”, Haqif Mulliqi with the plays “Four Epauettes”, “Kosovars”, “Perfumery”, “Claustrophobia”, Fadil Hysa with the plays “The frones”, “Faust”, “The Haze” etc. The extreme transformations and alienations that these authors realize with their characters are not done outside of finding a motivation and their own artistic logic. They specifically mix two worlds, two spaces, two states, the real one and the one invented by fantasy. The characters are as much animated as they are human characters, in which they play with symbioses of the type of mythological creatures, of the living with the dead, of the human with the material. Thanks to these symbioses, symbolic and metaphorical layers with sensitive hypnotic and artistic power have been realized.

In many postmodern performances, a paradoxical mixture has been made by playing with the illogical, the surprising, the actions that lose meaning, which remains such until the end (meaningless); illusions and self-deception are deliberately confused, on the one hand, with the real situation of man, in a world were chaos, confusion, absurdity, lack of

goals, on the other hand. This type of drama, mostly produced after World War II, and therefore the despair that had gripped the world, the absurdity of the behavior and actions of society with the terrible bloodshed during it, appeared in Albanian dramaturgy and theatre in Kosovo in the late 1960s and early 1970s. Contesting frozen norms turned into rituals and formal behaviour without content, criticism and satire of the destructive power of abusive power, the meaning and misunderstanding of freedom, the attitude towards oneself, the problem of personality, etc., became its favourite themes. In this case, poetic elements gained priority, while the themes themselves became more abstract, more symbolic. The semantic undertones are hidden, often revealed through irony, humour, the grotesque, where absurd actions, strange and paradoxical behaviour, foolish gestures and words are encountered.

Thanks to the applications in the elements of form, Albanian theater, especially after the 2000s, managed to better express the interactive relationships between denotation and connotation in the dramatic text, mostly in the conception of the word, dialogue, text and subtext; the relationships of the tragic and the comic gained greater value, which now appear as opposing elements and vectors. The relationship with rhythm underwent reformations. In modern and postmodern drama, it gains another speed. Likewise, the relationships with dichotomies and antinomies as mutual forms change.

Modern and postmodern theatre in Albania has often appeared as a minimalist theatre, where the director relies mainly on the actor's play and the expressive power of his artistic findings. He has given priority in the performance to:

- a) the relationship between content and form, when a work with dramatic and tragic content is treated with elements of the comic, burlesque, grotesque;
- b) the relationship between gesture and word, which gains special space in the treatment of the acting game from the directorial treatment of the work;
- c) the relationship with the unexpected, through which the status quo of dialogue and action is broken, surprise and curiosity are created, catching the spectator by surprise;
- d) the relationship with the change of starting point, with contradiction and counterpoint.

These qualities have been seen more maturely in plays such as Eduardo de Filippo's "The Great Magic" and F. Durrenmat's "Visit of the Old Lady", directed by Gëzim Kame, "Six Characters Seek an Author" by Luigi Pirandello, directed by M. Xhelili, "Moonlight Night" by I. Kadare, directed by E. Budina, "Korça Carnival" by S. Çomora, directed by A. Basha, "Public Dinner" by T. Dervishi, directed by A. Selimi, "The Five Seasons of the Enemy of the People", directed by B. Neziri, "The Accidental Death of an Anarchist", directed by M. Kutali, "Faust", directed by F. Hysaj, "L'Avar" by Moliere, directed by Hervis Çuli, etc.

From the successful beginnings of modern Albanian direction were the plays "Erveheja" (1968), directed by Muharrem Qena, "Brown spot" (1969), directed by Mihal

Luarasi, “Arturo Ui” (1979), directed by Piro Mani and “The Bathhouse” (1973), directed by Kujtim Spahivogli.

The first play can be considered one of the most successful and fundamental theatrical productions of Albanian theatre in Kosovo. All its components brought talented ideas, figures, findings and approaches from both the direction and acting, as well as from the scenography, costume design, choreography and music.

The second play called for more humanism, personal freedom and a little more privacy and pleasure, in the climate when everything was socialized, controlled, dogmatic and “collective”. The play as a theatrical reality and conception had a modern, contemporary form, of a “different” theatre. In addition to the symbols and significant details with allegorical, symbolic and associative loads, it also brought an interesting theatrical structure, the CHORUS, as an interactive element, which interrupted the action from time to time by judging the behaviours and thoughts of the characters.

The third play had a visible aesthetic brilliance, where the new form, structure and theatrical innovation stood out in a sensational directorial conception and fantasy, full of findings, details, sharp satire, Gothic, dramatic and tragic situations, fear and horror. It was an interaction of the dramatic, poetic and tragic with the grotesque, sarcasm, criminal and perverted (ugly). In his relationship with the actors, the director Piro Mani followed contemporary methodology. On the one hand, he preserved the realistic play, on the other hand, he introduced the Brechtian effects of distancing, “play” and “fun” into the acting, effectively using the grotesque. The actor's interpretation developed on several levels: the dramatic, the pathetic, the hysterical, the comic, the grotesque, etc.

The fourth performance alternated ironic, sarcastic levels with the use of burlesque and grotesque, mocking the ideological and moral codes and taboos of communism. The theater brought Mayakovsky’s satirical drama into the context of the political situation in Albania, making moderations and interpretations accordingly. This was especially noticeable with the stigmatization of the “cult of the individual”, which directly alluded to the cult of the communist dictator Enver Hoxha. For their modernist concepts, the two directors, Mihal Luarasi and Kujtim Spahivogli, were punished by the dictatorship and imprisoned.

Through the staging of modern dramas, the theatre artists offered a mosaic of sensitivities towards the characters, who did not converge, but rather diverged towards each other as well as towards their own states during the course of stage time. They were no longer carriers of a well-defined historical time, but of a “super-time”, that is, a time that is universalizing. The same was done to the environment of the action, which escaped realistic details and became symbolic, metaphorical, ephemeral, often ambiguous, extremely conventional. Modern drama in Albania also no longer preferred formal coherence. It restructured the dialogue, its direct meaning, by now applying numerous semantic subtexts. Directorial conceptions discovered and evidenced in the stagings of the works of Albanian authors the opposition and denial of the principles of classical dramas, by affirming other aesthetic principles. These conceptions surpassed amorphous,

dead and exhausted forms. They performed literary operations that affected not simply the semantics of the text, but the “morphology” of the theater itself by suggesting other representations, other ways of elaboration and structures of the construction of the theatrical performance.

3. Discussion and Finding

The drama of the absurd is one of the types with great influence in modern world theatre. Its well-known parts are also commonly performed in Albanian theatre.¹ In these performances, the principles of “mimeitic”, naturalistic, realistic drama are rejected. They exceeded the principle of cause and effect, that of structural harmony of episodes as well as that of continuity of action. Its characters seem surprising, they lack psychosocial coherence, their social and class affiliations. Albanian directors such as Arben Kumbaro, Fadil Hysaj, Bekim Lumi, Altin Basha, Milto Kutali, Memet Xhelili, Agim Qirjaqi, Adonis Filipi, Ilir Bokshi, etc., by staging some of their works such as “Waiting for Godot”, “The Chairs”, “The Bald Singer”, “Rhinoceros”, “Happy Days”, “The King is Dying”, “The Teacher”, “The Lecture”, “The Future is in the Eggs”, “The Servants” etc., have brought these works into their own style and typology. They have broken down the codes and meaning of language and dialogue, treating them more than once as illogical relationships, as a collection of misunderstandings, as verbal rituals where meaning is lost, consequently making communication between characters and the works themselves, which have often been called anti-drama, particularly difficult. The directors have expressed their messages through difficult symbolism. They have required an elite, cultivated and aesthetically-pleasing spectator to decipher them, as they are characterized by multiplicity and overlapping meanings, by another way of communicating.

In many of the works of absurdist authors that have been staged in Albanian theater, the relationship between man and God, with the absolute, with the moral dictates of custom and social norms, with the existential anxiety that it causes and with the need for freedom and epiphany has occupied an important place. There, the processes of man's alienation from society, himself, and the world have also been accurately examined. In these performances, there has always been something secret, an enigma or mystical, occult power that has determined the behavior of the characters themselves. Fatality appears as a dominant phenomenon.

¹Although delayed, the arrival on the Albanian stage of distinguished works of this typology represented an encounter with a new, unfamiliar, and different dramaturgical poetics. The emergence of this dramaturgy had its own cultural, literary, and intellectual context. Naturally, it came after the numerous experiments that drama underwent in the twentieth century, recalling here a multitude of artistic and literary movements and trends such as surrealism, expressionism, and existentialism. Prominent playwrights, theatre theorists, and directors such as Antonin Artaud, Alfred Jarry, Maeterlinck, August Strindberg, Bertolt Brecht, Luigi Pirandello, Max Reinhardt, Hofmannsthal, Adolphe Appia, and others, interfered with and influenced the literary and artistic consciousness of Samuel Beckett, as one of the founders of the Theatre of the Absurd as a paradoxical scenic form.

One of the first plays or anti-dramas of the theater of the absurd in Albanian theater was S. Becket's "Waiting for Godot" on October 2, 1993. It was presented as an "experimental" theater at the Academy of Arts, directed by Arben Kumbaro. The play was well received by the audience, who had previously been deprived of modern European drama. They recognized the universal philosophical messages of this type of drama on the meaning of human being, his relations with the existential part of life, with verbal communication and internal psychic fractures, using the destructuring and alienation of characters, mythologizing techniques, etc. Becket's answer to Alan Schneider, the first American director of the play "Waiting for Godot", is well known.

When he asked him "What was the meaning of Godot", Becket replied: "If I knew, I would have said it right away in the play". Nothing happens, no one comes, no one leaves, it's all in vain, Beckett said about this part. This is because in the drama no concrete story is narrated, since the subject with concrete events is suppressed. Even the director A. Kumbaro discovered in the text the immutability, the static situation. He respected its anti-Aristotelian principles, that is, the rejection of the principle of cause and effect, of the structural harmony of episodes, of the continuity of action, of the internal psychophysical convergence, of the meaninglessness of language, of dialogue as a ritual and of the message through semantic subtexts. The director managed to treat with insight the relationship of man with God, with the absolute, without giving this a religious background:

"Creating a sense of the absurd in the spectator," the director asserted, "is nothing more than awakening from the banal lethargy of his daily life. Always breaking the pattern, breaking taboos will constitute resistance, will lead to psychic collapse. And this is normal. It will happen once... I would say that today the absurd is not experienced only by Albanians. It is a fellow traveler of the chaos that has gripped almost all countries of the East" (Flori, 2001).

The play made evident the process of man's alienation from society, himself, the world, his undeserved suffering. The idea of rigid social hierarchies was outlined, where the dominant relationship usually remained that between master and slave, between the active and the passive, between the dreamer and the ordinary man, between the optimist and the pessimist. These antinomies of a universal nature were expressed in the changing and unchanging relationships between Agim Qirjaqi's Estragon and Gulielm Radoja's Vladimir. In this play, what the renowned Beckett scholar Niklaus Gessner underlined was seen:

"More important than any formal sign of the disintegration of language and meaning in Beckett's plays is the nature of the dialogue itself, which again and again breaks, breaks, not as a result of dialectical changes in the flow of thought in it, but through the loss of meaning in individual words or through the inability of the characters to remember what exactly they were talking about" (Gessner, 1957).

It must be stated that these markings of Beckett's literary style are respected by the treatment given to the text, dialogues, monologues, retorts, sudden breaks in the dialogue, words left in suspense, etc. Arben Kumbaro's directorial reading made understandable parallels with the state of mind of the Albanian people in the early 1990s: depression, crisis, disintegration, poverty, lost hope, etc. The correct and accurate understanding and reading of the work, its signs, the psychoanalytic and anthropological approaches it has, its stylistic peculiarities and literary structures, became the primary condition for the correct and accurate performance of the drama on the theatrical stage. In an open stage, without curtains, arioses and backdrops, where the spectator's eye sees the dirty walls and supporting concrete of the Academy of Arts building, along with a deliberate mess of decorations left here and there backstage, two actors enter: Agim Qirjaqi as Vladimir and Gulielm Radoja as Estragon. They walk and spin around the stage. Somewhere near the center, slightly to the right is a dry, fake tree. There is only one large leaf hanging and ready to be snapped. The spectator tries to decode this image and *mise-en-scène* as the emptiness of nature and the soul.

The director has insisted on making transcendence understandable, the communication of man with fate, with the intangible power, which is projected as a constant struggle and search from the outside in and from the inside out, to understand what is not visible and to ironize the rule of illusions in the consciousness of the tired man. Such an idea, not easily grasped and visible in Beckett's text, was carefully internalized in its content. The director "plays" with the *mise-en-scène*, the wanderings left and right of Vladimir and Estragon, he plays with the dialogue that loses its thread and meaning, which resumes right where it has finished, he plays with the clothing and behavior of the actors in the respective roles. Although in the form of presentation everything seems meaningless and as if in a vicious circle where the last becomes the beginning and vice versa, in fact the meaning lies in the alternating character of the literary sign, that is, in the stripping of illusions and the awareness of man about the state of fluctuations, uncertainty and ambiguity of his identity, categorically rejecting didactics and any rhetoric that bombards man day and night with all kinds of doctrines, media or social impacts. The anxious waiting for Godot was transformed into something ridiculous. The discussion took the form of a chatter about the nature of hope and despair. Through laughter and a dismissive attitude, sadness was revealed. A sharp mind could discern there the terrible silhouette of the tragic, the exhausting sorrow that was hidden behind the clownery.

The four characters Vladimir and Estragon, Pocco and Lucky are dependent on each other, they need presence and communication, they want to share their existence mutually. The actors conveyed the anxious flow of their troubled souls, internalizing it in each one. This created a chaos and psychic "mess" almost without an address, without knowing the cause of what came from it and why it was created. Everything remained something vague, ephemeral, not concrete, not clearly perceptible. Gulielm Radoja brought an Estragon tired from running and walking, being less persistent, unstable, while

Agim Qirjaqi brought a Vladimir filled with an almost grotesque optimism and an inner joy, being persistent in his goal. Through a *mise-en-scène* that sometimes “napped” on the stage floor and sometimes ran around it, sometimes in a rush and sometimes in peace, the spectator saw the two opposite sides of man, who was in fact ONE but divided into two characters: body and soul. The contradictions of their characters, as the researcher (Lisa Missing, 2007) emphasizes in her study of Becket’s characters, are numerous and continuous. They are tearful natures of each other; they depend on each other and always stay together.

It is precisely the contradictions between the two main characters that Arben Kumbaro has resolved by applying several plans:

- a) the rhythmic one of speech;
- b) the physical and plastic one with opposite modeling: Qirjaqi energetic and dynamic, while Radoja flashy and passive;
- c) the psychorhythmic one, the first with choleric temperaments, the second phlegmatic;
- d) that of analytical psychology where the first displays the symbolic model of the mind, the behaviour of the rational, masculine, ruling person, who speaks and leads, while the second prefers the symbolic model of the soul, the feminine passivity, submissive, listening, who is led by the other, that is, the “spiritual” model;
- e) that of alternation and transition from one to the other, such as the relationship between Pozzo and Lucky, who are as contradictory as Vladimir and Estragon.

Ahmet Pasha’s Pozzo was presented as a sadistic teacher, a cappadocia, while Niko Kanxheri’s Lucky was one of the most brilliant figures of the play, perhaps the most grotesque, the most “Beckettian”, the most prominent, extremely special. Kumbaro's direction has not lacked a sense of humour and fun, preserving the form of a mystery of what happens in the ups and downs of the two wanderers, as well as in the mental, verbal and physical parody between Pozzo and Lucky. He has not even excluded elements of clownery and circus, which are ubiquitous in Becket's plays and plays. And just when fun and entertainment seem to be the essentials, something unexpected happens, a counterpoint psychic reaction and the spectator makes an almost "pindaric" leap, abandoning the entertaining, funny and comical side and suddenly discovering a deep, sad truth. Behind the joke, one sees human ruins whose destruction is regrettable. There is no explanation. Only silence, which, as if unwillingly, enters the souls of the spectators and creates in them a deep catharsis.

Additionally, typologies of absurd drama have been used by many Albanian authors, initially in Kosovo where the paths of artistic creation were more open. Among them, the most prominent was Anton Pashku with the plays “Gof” and “Syncopation”. Then come Beqir Musliu, Teki Dervishi, Rexhep Qosja, Resul Shabani, Fadil Hysaj, Haqif Mulliqi, Nebi Islami, Jeton Neziraj, Naser Shatrolli, etc. In Albania, this literary model was followed only after 1990 due to the strict censorship that the regime had imposed on

modern and postmodern literature. However, partial elements are found in the works of Kasem Trebeshinës, Stefan Çapalik, Ferdinand Hysi, Serafin Fankos, Teodor Laço, etc. In their works and stage performances, directors have emphasized the strong violations of the principles of traditional drama. We are bringing to your attention two plays and two Albanian authors who have successfully delivered modern drama of the absurd type.

From madness to sorrow, grief, tragedy “*Three minds at auction*” by Ferdinand Hysi in two directorial versions

The play was staged for the first time by director Armando Boro at the “Petro Marko” theatre in Vlora in 1996 and was welcomed by the audience. The play brought innovation for the time in the way it was conceived, the form of presentation, the characters, the dialogue, etc. It was called a play of the theatre of the absurd type, while with the unexpected, paradoxical ending and the revelation of the true state of the characters, it was also called a successful attempt towards an existentialist approach (Papagjoni, 2011). In fact, in the drama there is a connection between existentialist theatre and the theatre of the absurd. Even in this drama, its characters seem fragmented, while in reality they have an internal coherence in their own conception, they are self-sufficient, so to speak, therefore unchangeable. Such are also treated by the director A. Boro and the actors who played the main roles: Vasil Goda, Astrit Mamaj, Hatiqet Bendo, etc.

The play seems like a game of mentally ill people, a kind of quarrel and fadom that acquires political undertones and that makes associations with the political reality of the early '90s in Albania through the four main characters, who are identified as: the left, the right, the center and the people. In this play of the mentally ill, director A. Boro suddenly creates what in literary criticism of absurd dramaturgy was considered the superstitiousness of the circumstance of presentation, which came in the form of nonsense and mystification:

- a) I have something to say and
- b) what I am saying can be understood.

By using the conventional language of drama, especially the form of presenting the characters as mentally ill, this convention, unlike the dramas of the absurd theater that leave them in a latent and unchanged state, on the contrary here the characters create a strong emotional rupture. Through this technique, their dramatic past is suddenly revealed, the reason why they are there, in a psychiatric hospital, why they were abandoned, by whom, what serious troubles they have had in life?! If the play, regarding the mental state of the characters, operates with the presentational forms of the theater of the absurd, while their behaviors are completely incomprehensible and motivated by logic, it is different with the sudden end of the play, as the actors in their roles already acquire the logic of what has happened to them before. This motivates their abnormal behaviors. This play breaks the first state and applies another type of stage convention, which is related to the effect of displacement and sudden change. In this case, the change

of state leads the spectator from the joke to the real state, from the meaningless to the deep meaning, from the comic to the tragic.

In his famous book “The Myth of Sisyphus”, Albert Camus wrote:

“Absurdity arises from a comparison... It stems from the comparison between a factual situation and a certain reality, between an action and a world that surpasses it. The absurd is essentially a divorce. It is not in either of the two elements of the comparison. It arises from their confrontation.” (Camus, 1992).

It is precisely the confrontation of the two states of the characters in the drama “Three Minds at Auction”, the beginning and the end, that makes the absurd a form of social criticism and a burning irony. Director A. Boro has given his support to the construction of a surprising, paradoxical story. It is attractive in itself, but it is not easy to narrate; it required insight so that the paradox would not lose its ideological and emotional effect. He needed to motivate and justify the behaviours of the drama's characters through careful treatment of the actors' play as a duality of states, logical and illogical, before and after the moment when they return to their normal state. We are bringing to your attention two plays and two Albanian authors who have successfully delivered modern drama of the absurd type.

“The Four Epauettes” by Haqif Mulliq (1993)

It is a drama that has the tendency of the typology of the absurd. Through two characters who bear the incessant war and cause it, generals Alfadori and Betadori, the causes of wars are analyzed as an expression of crazy ambition and destructive careers, which come in two approaches, the illusory one and the real one: what is desired and intended and what is made impossible by the resistance and protest of the peoples. The events are set at the crossroads of two wars, what has been done and has left behind ruins, wounds, injuries and what is being prepared to be done. The two generals, as their two conventional names, A and B (Alpha-Beta) have; are also duplicitous of each other. “The moment they realize that life is above death, it is precisely death that snatches them away, transforming their effort into a pure null. Metaphors and symbolic overlaps with characters such as Grajeti, who simultaneously performs three functions: the blind, the deaf, death; or the pair of naked young people, who imitate the original sin, - usually bring paradigms of the drama of the absurd”, assesses J. Papagjoni (2012).

Directed by Haqif Mulliq himself, this drama brings situations through modern structures. They are projected in the form of chaotic states, with a visible mobility of thoughts that go from one direction to the other. The environment is undefined, the space of action is conventionalized especially in the extreme, it turns into symbolism in function of the author's intention: the destructive consequences of wars. The procedure of action and events favors the absence, or rather the loss of the thread of connection and reasoning of the argument being examined. Thus, a lack of coherence is created in the various vicissitudes of the subject: the beginning and resumption of the same ingrained idea, the fantasies and hallucinations that come in the form of paranoia. In this case, time loses its

normal flow, sometimes it goes forward and sometimes it goes back. The characters are unchangeable. On the other hand, the actions of the characters lose their logical sense, they become absurd.

What happens is what Ionesco emphasized in his essay on Kafka that “the absurd is that which is deprived of a purpose:

... *Disconnect from its religious, metaphysical and transcendental roots and man is lost; all his actions become absurd, useless, meaningless.*” (Esslin, 1961)

It is precisely in this drama that the discovery of the metaphysical anxiety that the two generals experience, intertwined with the existential anxiety of the outbreak of a war and the destruction of human lives, converges precisely with the directorial idea of A. Mulliqi as a playwright and director at the same time, making the absurdity of their thinking, the devaluation of human ideals, the lack of spiritual purity and the triumph of the unbridled ego distinct. In the dialogue of the two actor-generals, the drama keeps the dialogue in the tones of a rhetorical discourse, often even cynical towards each other, removing such ideological and philosophical parallels that constitute the central themes in the dramas of the absurd, including especially the pieces of Ionesco, Adamov, Genet, Giraud, Anouilh, Salacrus, etc.

Alfadori and Betadori, although they claim to defend their causes and appear to be two opposing positions, are in fact the same coin: death. Yesterday's war and today's (expected) war are the same. Both try to give reason and justification to their existence as bearers of war. They are identical to each other. This is evident in their logic, but also in the costumes, the settings and movements positioned at the two ends of the stage. In their dialogue made at a distance, the ironies and mutual oppositions actually make the spectator aware of the human catastrophe that war brings. It is necessary to take into account the time when the drama was written, the year 1993. The former Yugoslav Federation was rapidly disintegrating. Wars between its republics had broken out. Their destructive consequences had become quite clear on the horizon, where no people was a "winner", on the contrary, a loser. The nationalist myths that fueled wars were falling.

To superimpose the element of absurdity on the drama and the play, the author and director H. Mulliqi created such symbolism that came from the layers of biblical myth, such as the introduction of two children, a boy and a girl, who seem to imitate the biblical parable of the “first sin”, the biting of the forbidden apple, where God’s curse began; as a result, suffering, debauchery, misfortune, evil. Another symbol came through the character of Grajet, who is simultaneously blind, deaf and stuttering. Such was the self-destructive action of the generals through devastating wars, where the truth is not seen, reason is not heard and the purpose is hidden. The symbolism led automatically to totalitarian and dictatorial regimes where freedom is lacking and where man, out of fear of punishment, does not see, does not hear, does not speak. Then there was the symbol of the cave, which remained after the destructive nuclear war. It drips water. Water has healing properties for the eyes, so that after darkness and destruction man can see the light, the truth, the path, life.

The dialogues between the two generals are ruled by the impossibility of resolution and meaninglessness. Absurdity accompanies them throughout the dialogue. A contradiction is often created between what is seen on stage and what is said. For this reason, the principle of the rejection of the subject as a description of one or several events, as well as that of anthropomorphism and empathy towards this or that character, operates. Both are antiheroes. This has therefore stimulated the form of “anti-literary” drama, avoiding the elements of detailed narration, that is, the rejection of the “literary”, while the reasonable and the seemingly “noble” purpose, ends in a paradoxical solution and annihilation.

“These characters, in essence, are possessed by disappointment, by the feeling of absurdity, of the anxiety of hopeless waiting,” analyzes Besim Rexha, “which is intended to be neutralized through various actions in that extreme existential situation, actions that produce and deepen the further absurdity of their situation.” (Rexhaj, 2009).

The absurd becomes particularly evident at the end of the play, when the two generals, aware of their expected death, want to hang themselves with a rope because they understand that everything is a futility, that the meaning of war is precisely its absurdity, while at the moment when they see a hope of life as the gate opens slightly and they remove the ropes of self-hanging from their throats, it is precisely then that death appears to them with the face of Grajet.

In accordance with the typology of the drama of the absurd, in the stage conception of the plays of Albanian authors, the fact that there is a state of waiting is noted, which increases the dramatic suspense. This is achieved through what is not seen, what is not understood, what is hidden, what causes panic and horror, what has a constant threat within (Slatina, 2001). The characters seem to be fixated on something that is wandering “somewhere” and that creates tension, or on something that is ordinary and is considered fundamental and of particular importance. Dramas such as, for example, "Syncope" and "Gof" by Anton Pashku, "Eternal Dream", "Museum", "The Trojan War", "The Legend of the One Who Went Away", "Fear and Crime" by Kasem Trebeshina, "The Paper Moon" by Mehmet Krajë, "Public Dinner" by Teki Dervishi, "Allegretto Albania" and "Shoes" by Stefan Çapalik, "In Front of the Traffic Light" by F. Hysi, etc., use the mythologizing technique: either by using ancient myths, or by creating literary myths through fiction, giving the invented characters a clear human content. The event, as a driving engine and a reflective and presenting element, loses its importance. Their directors have treated both the narrative and the connecting links of events as elements that reject, and even destroy, the model of the classical drama plot. Now the episodes sometimes have no internal connection with each other, on the contrary they break the fabled chain of cause and effect, transforming into an almost "random" connection, scattered and seemingly without logical order. Internally, on the contrary, they have their own inviolable dramaturgical reasoning.

In the way directors have brought the narrative of the works, the technique of mixing and amalgamating fragments, dialogues through multiple inversions, the creation of oppositions and contradictions, parallel montages, etc. is increasingly popular with them. The normal progression according to an ascending order from the exposition, to the climax and to the final resolution that follows (the catastrophe) is no longer respected. Somewhere the end turns into the beginning and somewhere else the beginning becomes the end. In the vitalization of these dramas, directors have created cycles of actions that follow each other, since they have applied several well-known principles of modern and postmodern drama, such as the dissolution of dramatic action, its divergence and fragmentation, the widespread application of retrospectives, the return of events, dialogues, the same words and sentences in the form of verbal rituals. Another characteristic of these dramas with closeness to absurdist modeling is the treatment of conflict. It avoids direct forms and camouflages itself through the situation, symbolism, and specific structuring of the literary subject, aiming for its depth and concealment. Directors have made visible the second plans, the veiled and hidden implications, which are given through another form, not direct but diverse. For example, from the dramatic and tragic one passes to the comic and grotesque and vice versa; or from rhetoric one passes to the poetic, from what initially comes veiled and hidden to what later appears openly and is declared, etc.

By preferring the visibility of events and actions, ritual states, dramas of the absurd model in Albanian dramaturgy after 1990 have increased their communicative sense by conveying more understanding and convergent layers of meanings, which have made the texts polyvalent. For specific ideas and purposes, in specific scenic parts, the discourse has come as a seemingly chaotic manifestation of the existential situation of the characters, of the fatality and the tragedy of communication as such. If we analyse the dramatic works of Kasem Trebeshina, at the time when he was in prison, the language their atrophies, becomes deliberately difficult, loses its direct communicative function. It exceeds the agreement between two beings or more, while through successive misunderstandings humour is caused, the ironic and mocking sense is emphasized, using logical collisions and word games. This is observed for example in “Museum”, “Odin Modvalsen”. These make logical propositions escape from their initial meanings, as a result they turn into misunderstandings and absurdity.

The same thing happens with the play “Three Minds at Auction” regarding the characters’ words and their play, as well as with the relationships of the mentally ill with the NGO worker, who would take care of the sick with umbrellas (to protect them from the holes in the leaking roof) and with the homeless (because the bathrooms are broken). The characters of “Hana”, Mephisto and the Masks take on a sharp form in the play “Paper Moon”, author Mehmet Kraja, director Fadil Hysaj. Between the initial meaning of the words and the meaning they later acquire, the opposition between the high and the low, the sharp and the stupid, the parasitic that is served as “philosophical” and the philosophical that is reduced to banalities is created. Examined from the perspective of

an aesthetic, let's call it "relativist", as a dialogical discourse structure this has pronounced features and elements of the drama of the absurd, which differs essentially from realistic drama.

The modernist form of dialogue and generally that of "logos", in the case of this drama, is marked by director Hysaj among the original and most active elements of the play. Often called "anti-drama", even in the drama "Paper Moon" the director has operated precisely with the deliberate blow that has been made to meaning and logic by playing with meaninglessness and illogicality. While in the texts of the plays "Perfumery", "Trains", "Claustrophobia", "Four Epauettes", the author and director Haqif Mulliqi has effectively used dialogues, which have a more closed form, are hermetic, with double meanings, with wordplay, their ritual repetitions. These are identified precisely as avant-garde dramatic structures and not as realistic dramatic structures.

4. Conclusion

Thanks to the works of postmodern playwrights (S. Becket, E. Ionesco, F. Arabal, H. Pinter, A. Camus, L. Pirandello, D. Fo, H. Muller, P. Vais, C. Churchill, etc.) and their staging, the Albanian spectator became acquainted with the presentation of new concepts and principles. He managed to rediscover, confront or contradict those that were conceived differently compared to other typologies of the drama genre. Our directorship was especially acquainted with surrealism, expressionism, existentialism, absurdism, postmodernism and its most sensational styles, with the famous names of world theater directors who had staged them such as Antonine Artaud, Alfred Jarry, Maurice Meaterelinck, Jacques Copeau, further with Max Reinhard, Bertold Brecht, George Strehler, Jerzi Grotowsky, Peter Brook, Julian Beck, Robert Wilson, Erwin Piscator, Luca Rankoni, Robert Wilson, etc. Within their knowledge, they managed to bring the originality and innovations that modern drama brought in the way of conceiving characters, in the structure and technique of their stage vision, in the form of actorial discourse and theatrical language in general.

An interesting solution in the pieces staged has been to bring the effect of restructuring the language of the characters through the creation of the "tragedy of communication", when the word is devalued through verbal ritual and ironic discourse. In many plays, the game with the diverse and contradictory meanings of the word has been used, often from the positions of the solipsist brought the suffering of the Albanian man that comes from freedom or captivity, the tragedy caused by dilemmas and impossibilities in choosing a path, direction, goal. Often and more often the mission of man in these works is either limited by impossibility, or has turned into disaster, or has ended in a dead end. In their unfolding, the theater has illuminated the existential crossroads of the characters. They are usually accompanied by suffering, spiritual upheavals, contradictions between the goal and the means, between a noble mission and pragmatic and even banal solutions, consequently transforming its meaning into a tool for disrupting logical cohesion, sound

reasoning and the presentation of a clear goal. In some plays, these have been turned upside down, justifying it with the impossibility of the self (the character) to know himself and his connection with the other. Recognizing the principle of discourse, the form in which it is carried out between actors in their roles, directors have transformed speech from a means of communication and connection into a lack of communication and an impossibility of connection. It is, at best, minimalist. Directors have deliberately narrowed the boundary between what is serious and primary and what is ridiculous, sarcastic and irrelevant.

Regarding what has been called “existentialist drama”, associated with the models of the plays of Jean Paul Sartre (Jan Pol Sartri) and some of his followers, especially with the plays of Camus, to some extent Jean Genet, Fernando Arrabal, etc., in Albania and Kosovo there have been several playwrights who have applied it. Their dramas have dealt with man’s problems with being, with himself, with fear and anxiety, with the absolute. These features are especially prominent in the corpus of Teki Dervishi's plays, including the nine-part trilogy "The Shore of Sorrow” as well as his other plays "Freedom Reprise", "Publike Dinner", "The Exhumation of Peter Bogdani” etc. In these plays, the same features are observed that are observed in existentialist dramas. Severe dramatic and existential situations are encountered, within them a great psychic tension is felt, where anxiety overwhelms the characters. They have lost their inner peace and harmony, they are characterized by disintegrating and senseless actions, by existential trauma and suffering, moving from normal to abnormal, from logical to illogical, in search of something that challenges their lives and normality. Similar properties are also evident in Beqir Musliu's two tetralogies "The Witch of Gjelhan" and "The roll" with eight parts.

The dramatic event here creates eddies and collisions of characters in action, counteractions, confrontations with each other, and all together offer a unique flow in which they intertwine, clash and mutually hurt each other. In this way, the dramas reveal a kind of moral choreography, which is also the essence of their dramatic action. In their psychic interiors as modern and postmodern playwrights, Albanian directors have discovered spiritual relationships and reports of an eternal nature, where a deep and rich symbolism moves, which has dimensioned the universal direction of the works. They have usually been accompanied by suffering, spiritual turmoil, and the contradictions between a noble mission and its pragmatic - sometimes even banal - solutions.

Conflict of interests

The authors would like to confirm that there is no conflict of interests associated with this publication and there is no financial fund for this work that can affect the research outcomes.

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